

A classical perfect fluid model satisfying Maxwell's equations in vacuum

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Temporal note

Work developed during undergraduate studies in Physics at the University of Turin
(1995–1997).

Mathematical result systematized and completed in 2002.

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Author's note

I originally developed the present work during my studies at the University of Turin, in particular following my study of atmospheric physics in the years between 1995 and 1997. During my first years of teaching Mathematics, Physics, and Computer Science at the “E. Agnelli” Technical Institute, I continued to refine and clarify the content of this study.

In 2002 I systematized and completed the mathematical isomorphism discussed here, concerning a class of classical perfect fluids subject to explicit simplifying hypotheses, which allow one to derive Maxwell's equations in vacuum and to establish a formal relationship between classical electromagnetism and fluid dynamics.

A relevant observation that emerges from this structural analogy is that the invariance of Maxwell's equations under Lorentz transformations—one of the cornerstones of modern physics—turns out to be compatible with the simplifying hypotheses introduced in the model. In particular, assuming the validity of the wave equation for the velocity field, a strong hypothesis but coherent within a small-oscillation regime, leads to a Lorentz-invariant mathematical structure.

Within the analogy explored here, this circumstance suggested the possibility of interpreting special relativity as an emergent phenomenology from a deeper description formulated in terms of a classical continuous medium. This observation identifies a possible conceptual framework for the development of emergent approaches to relativity.

Throughout my study of modern physics I have always retained the desire not to abandon completely the idea of an ether describable as a continuous medium endowed with mechanical properties—yet not as a solid or rigid medium, in the sense of an absolute reference frame ruled out by the Michelson–Morley experiment—but rather as a fluid, or as a material with a more complex rheology, in which wave propagation takes place within a dynamic, possibly turbulent environment. The electromagnetic–mechanical analogy presented in this work represents a formalized result stemming from that reflection.

The analogy developed still left open some fundamental aspects. In particular, the nature of electric charge is not addressed, since the analysis is limited to Maxwell's equations in vacuum, in the absence of charges and currents. Consequently, the problem of the interaction between electromagnetic field and matter is not resolved within this scheme.

Likewise, the Lorentz force is not derived here in a complete sense, since its formulation would require the explicit introduction of electric charge as a source and as a dynamical parameter of the interaction. However, already in the original phase of developing this work, I observed that the magnetic part of the Lorentz force has a mathematical structure formally analogous to that

of certain apparent forces that arise in non-inertial reference frames, in particular the Coriolis force. This analogy, well known in the literature, is to be understood in a structural and formal sense, without constituting, at the present stage, a complete physical explanation, but leaving it as an open field of research.

The result obtained therefore consists in a self-contained structural analogy, presented here without integrations or subsequent developments. For personal and professional reasons, I did not immediately pursue the exploration of the consequences of this work, which remained unpublished for several years.

This publication makes the result available in its original form, as a documented stage of a research path.

Abstract

In this work it is shown that, under an explicit set of dynamical and kinematical assumptions, the description of a classical, non-viscous and nearly incompressible perfect fluid can be put in formal correspondence with Maxwell's equations in vacuum.

Assuming the absence of advective terms, the validity of a wave equation for the velocity field, and the condition of vanishing divergence, one introduces a set of identifications between fluid-dynamical quantities and electromagnetic fields that reproduces exactly the mathematical structure of electromagnetism in the absence of charges and currents.

The result is purely structural in character and does not intend to provide a definitive physical interpretation, nor to address the problem of the origin of electric charge or the interaction between field and matter.

1 Introduction

This work has a limited and precise aim: to show that, under clearly stated dynamical and kinematical hypotheses for a classical perfect fluid, the equations governing a particular regime of the velocity field and pressure can be put in formal correspondence with Maxwell's equations in vacuum.

The interest of the result is structural in nature: it does not propose a complete physical theory of the vacuum nor a definitive reinterpretation of electromagnetism, but rather a demonstration of the existence of a mathematical isomorphism between a system of equations of classical fluid dynamics (under restrictive conditions) and electromagnetism in the absence of charges and currents.

2 Maxwell's equations in vacuum

We recall Maxwell's equations in vacuum:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \tag{2}$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \tag{3}$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \tag{4}$$

3 Fluid-dynamical hypotheses

Consider a non-viscous perfect fluid in the absence of external forces and gravitational fields. Its dynamics is governed by Euler's equation:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = -\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} \tag{5}$$

We introduce the following hypotheses:

1. Suppression of the advective term:

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (6)$$

2. Validity of the wave equation for the velocity field:

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (7)$$

3. Incompressibility condition:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (8)$$

4 Field identifications

We introduce the following identifications between electromagnetic quantities and fluid-dynamical variables:

$$\mathbf{B} \equiv \nabla \times \mathbf{v} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{E} \equiv \frac{\nabla p}{\rho} \quad (10)$$

5 Proof of the formal equivalence

From Euler's equation (5) and hypothesis (6), recalling that

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v}, \quad (11)$$

we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} = -\frac{\nabla p}{\rho}. \quad (12)$$

Taking the divergence of (12) and using (8):

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} \right) = 0, \quad (13)$$

which reproduces equation (1).

Equation (2) follows directly from the identity:

$$\nabla \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}) = 0. \quad (14)$$

Taking the curl of (12) yields:

$$\nabla \times \left(\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} \right) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}), \quad (15)$$

which reproduces equation (3).

Finally, using the vector identity:

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{v} = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) - \nabla^2 \mathbf{v}, \quad (16)$$

together with (8) and the wave equation (7), one obtains:

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{v} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} \right), \quad (17)$$

which reproduces equation (4).

6 Conclusions

Under the stated hypotheses, the dynamics of a classical perfect fluid reproduces exactly Maxwell's equations in vacuum. The result is structural in nature: it establishes a mathematical isomorphism between a particular regime of classical fluid dynamics and electromagnetism in the absence of charges and currents.